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Actionable and understandable? Evidence-based recommendations for the design of (multi-)hazard warning messages

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ABSTRACT

Communicating event-related hazard information can help prompt effective public responses and, consequently, reduce injuries and fatalities. Real-time information is commonly communicated to the public through multi-hazard platforms. However, whether these platforms' messages are correctly understood and whether they increase people's intention to take action is yet to be proven. We thus aimed at compiling recommendations on how to develop actionable and understandable (multi-)hazard warning messages. To this end, we designed various multi-hazard overviews and hazard messages, which were refined during the five virtual workshops we conducted with experts (N = 15) from different fields. We then surveyed (N = 601, between-subjects experiment) the Swiss public to check whether our designs increase people's intention to take action and help them correctly interpret the information presented. The design of the hazard overviews, we found, exerted no significant effect on people's intention to take action, probably because the participants showed a generally high interest in seeking further information. In contrast, the hazard overviews with time and action indications significantly increased people's understanding of whether they should take immediate actions. Moreover, adding a time- and action-related icon to the hazard messages significantly increased people's intention to take action. For both hazard overviews and messages, people's intention to take action was found to be proportional to the hazard's severity and urgency and influenced by various personal factors, such as past hazard experiences. To conclude, rendering information on multi-hazard platforms more actionable can prompt public responses and, in turn, increase society's resilience toward disasters.

1. Introduction

Owing to the high economic value of built environments, growing population, and frequent anthropogenic-induced processes – climate change, political conflicts, and so on – societies have become increasingly vulnerable to various natural and sociotechnical hazards. Despite our better knowledge about these hazards, the damage caused by them are continuously increasing [1]; for example, the yearly average number of fatalities due to large earthquake events still remain high [2]. Hazard and risk communication, if created

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and disseminated appropriately, can help prompt an effective public response and reduce injuries and casualties [3].

There are several approaches to communicate hazard and risk information [4]. In the last decades, communication via digital devices has increased rapidly. Meteorological services worldwide have implemented Multi-Hazard Impact-Based Warning Systems (MHIEWS) to consistently inform those potentially affected. Recently, the communication platforms used for this purpose have been expanded to include other natural hazards, such as wildfires or earthquakes, and sociotechnical hazards, such as chemical accidents or public health threats [5]. To this end, maps and messages that are compatible and consistent with the different hazards must be developed. This would allow the dissemination of information about cascading effects [6] and eliminate the need to download separate apps for different hazards.

However, providing information about multiple hazards on a single platform presents various challenges. First, multiple messages can overwhelm the public and cause confusion or inaction [7]. Second, hazards differ by their nature, intensity, return period, and societal effects, which limits the comparability between them and complicates the aim of having consistent hazard messages [8]. Third, users' personal factors – perceived behavioral control, literacy skills, and so on – determine whether they can use the information to take (protective) action [9]. Fourth, for weather-related hazards, people struggle to understand that they receive regular forecasts but that for earthquakes they mainly receive post-event information [10]. This differentiation is crucial because only then people know whether immediate actions are needed or not.

This study addressed these challenges from a societal perspective with the aim to provide recommendations on how to design actionable and understandable hazard overviews and messages with clear time indications. We focused on overviews and messages since they are the main information on multi-hazard platforms. When people visit these platforms, they first see an overview of the current hazards on the landing page. By clicking on a hazard, they are forwarded to a subpage with detailed information. Besides the design, we also assessed how people's personal factors, such as gender, age, educational degree, living place, and work position, and the factors of the theory of planned behavior affect their intention to take action and their interpretation of the information presented. Understanding the influence of these factors is crucial to tailor the communication products to specific abilities and needs. We thus aimed at answering the overarching research question: *How to design clearly understandable and actionable multi-hazard overviews and hazard messages, and which influence do personal factors have?*

To answer this research question, we first iteratively refined our designs of the overviews and messages during the five virtual workshops we conducted with scientists and practitioners from different fields. We then tested these designs by conducting a between-subjects experiment survey of the Swiss public, which helped us analyze the effects of the designs and the personal factors on people's intention to take action and their ability to correctly interpret the information. Further, we assessed whether the best-rated designs were also the ones that triggered people to take action (see Appendix B1 for the study design); because whether a person likes a design may also determine whether they use it. Since we tested the hazard overviews and messages for earthquakes, thunderstorms, COVID-19, and chemical accidents, our results are valuable not only for multi-hazard communication products but also for single hazards.

2. Theoretical and practical background

Responsible authorities, such as civil protection or national hazard institutions, use different channels to inform or warn the public about hazards. While most of them operate their own websites and convey information via their social media accounts [11–13], others additionally use emergency apps [14,15]. Further, they disseminate messages through traditional channels, such as television, radio, and sirens, or via cell broadcasting [16]. Regarding the latter, in many European countries, including Switzerland, cell broadcasting has no legal framework. Thus, to make sure that only people who are affected by a hazard receive the hazard messages on a multi-hazard app, access to users' GPS location or pre-selected warning areas is required [17]. Due to technological advancements in recent years, the way society uses mobile devices during disasters has significantly changed [3,18], and real-time information is spread rapidly after disasters. If the communication channels belong to a trusted environment [19], bundled information can help counteract infodemic¹ [20], minimize the spread of misinformation, and ensure that people can access reliable information [21]. Thereby, it is important that the institutions in charge only communicate what they are legally allowed to, avoiding trials such as the ones in L'Aquila (Italy) in 2009 [22] and the White Island (New Zealand) in 2019 [23].

We focused on mobile devices because their penetration rate in many countries is high, and mobile telecommunication networks cover many parts of the world [16]. Further, we focused on multi-hazard apps since the public demanded them [17] and since short message services (SMS) and cell broadcasting services (CBS) have already been researched [3,24]. In contrast, there has been no research on how the design of multi-hazard overviews and hazard messages influences people's intention to take action and their ability to correctly interpret the information provided. Moreover, distinguishing between various hazard events is important because the type of hazard influences the requirements for effective communication [25], and hazards are perceived differently when presented together with other hazards [26]. Therefore, to analyze the effect of design, we created various multi-hazard overviews and messages based on the best practices and recent insights from scientific studies (summarized in sections 2.1 and 2.2). This allowed us to answer our first research question (RQ1): *How should multi-hazard overviews and hazard messages be designed to increase people's intention to take action and ensure the correct interpretation of the information presented?*

Further, using the scale from Marti et al. [27], who analyzed earthquake hazard maps, we assessed people's general design perceptions. In our study on early earthquake warnings, we found that people do not necessarily prefer designs that trigger them to take

¹ "An infodemic is too much information including false or misleading information in digital and physical environments during a disease outbreak." [Source: https://www.who.int/health-topics/infodemic#tab=tab_1; 27.09.2021].

action [28], so in this study we sought the answer to a second research question (RQ2): *Are the preferred designs also the ones that increase people's intention to take action and ensure the correct interpretation of the information presented in multi-hazard overviews and hazard messages?*

2.1. Hazard overviews

Though there are diverse approaches to design multi-hazard apps worldwide, they all try to communicate hazard and risk information to the public in a timely, feasible, consistent, and comprehensible manner to encourage people to stay informed and, if needed, take action [29]. On the landing page of many multi-hazard platforms, the current hazard situation is displayed on maps [17], with location-specific textual information below/beside them [30]. The public, one of our prior studies confirmed, prefers a single map that displays all active hazards [17].

Maps have several advantages. First, they enable visual representations of the hazards and risks across an entire region [31], which, unlike numerical risk representations, lead to greater risk avoidance [32,33]. Second, maps with icons and pictograms can be understood even by those who do not know the language of the message [34]. Third, maps' visual representations allow people to quickly gain information as to who should take action and who is not affected [24].

However, people often struggle to interpret information on maps [27,35]. Furthermore, there are times when many hazard messages are active, and the simultaneous display of information may overwhelm the map [36,37]. This, in turn, may harm people's ability to quickly understand which hazards demand (immediate) action. When people are under stress, the resources available for their working memory are reduced [38].

Hazard categorization also plays an important role. Ripberger et al. [39], for example, showed that when receiving information, those people assigned to higher-impact categories were likelier to take protective action against a tornado than those assigned to lower-impact categories. People also struggle to interpret the categories themselves, such as danger or warning, due to their ambiguity [40]. Many different categorizations are used, ranging from the three-level traffic light system of "information, warning, and alert" to the five-level system of "no hazard, low hazard, moderate hazard, high hazard, very high hazard." An in-depth study comparing these two systems is yet to be conducted.

Furthermore, hazard overviews must help people make fast decisions regarding which actions to take first. Especially on mobile devices, with their limited screen size, textual information should be transformed into relevant and easily understandable keywords and icons [41]. Estuar et al. [41] further suggested that (emergency) apps should summarize the information and order it according to the severity and urgency of the hazards. To trigger appropriate preventive actions, Kunz and Hurni [42] further suggested differentiating between general information and detailed information. For general information, a (national) map displaying multiple hazards may be appropriate. If the aim is to sensitize people and motivate them to take protective action, regional or local maps, since they will enable people to perceive their risk to be higher, are better suited [42]. However, as Weyrich et al. [43] showed, providing detailed information can also help people better understand threats and appropriately respond to warnings. Thus, a balance between detailed information and summarized information must be achieved.

2.2. Hazard messages

Several studies have assessed the five crucial information elements that should be included in hazard messages: hazard type, affected area, time, source, and guidance on what to do [24,44,45]. Regarding guidance, recent studies have shown that people prefer to receive a combination of pictured and written behavioral recommendations [17,46]. Research has even shown that pictograms increase public motivation, comprehension, and compliance with warnings [47] and fasten and improve cognitive processing [48]. In addition, graphical displays attract and hold people's attention better than textual information [49], which may motivate them to read the messages. Further, explaining how the behavioral recommendations help to reduce harm increases people's response efficacy and, consequently, their intention to take action [50]. Moreover, the source of the information should be an institution trusted by the receivers [45,51], so placing the source at the beginning of the message further increases the message's credibility [40].

In addition to these five information elements, some countries include further information in their hazard messages. For example, when making decisions, people consider the severity of the threat and the potential consequences of their decisions [52]. This is why impact-based forecasts and warnings (IBFW) are becoming a standard in many countries around the world [43,53]. People also prefer information about secondary hazards [54], a list with emergency numbers, and a link that forwards them to official websites with more detailed information [55], all of which can reduce milling [40]. Moreover, according to the participants of Mays et al. [19], information tailored to their own environment made it more easily actionable to them. To this end, it is important to use simple words and no jargon [56]. In addition to static information, interactive features, such as a sharing function, can also be embedded on the platforms [12,17,46,57].

Although we know the kind of information preferred in hazard messages, on multi-hazard platforms, people receive several messages for various hazards with different characteristics. This can lead to message overload [58,59], which may reduce people's awareness of these hazards and cause misconceptions. For example, people can mistake earthquake messages as forecasts, thinking of them as weather-related messages and not as post-event information [10]. This can have severe consequences. People may think that they have to prepare for an earthquake, even though it has already happened. This, in turn, can lead to a loss of trust in the received information. It can also happen the other way around. When people think that a weather event has already happened, they do not take any actions, but when the event occurs, they may incur avoidable losses. People can thus mistake situations that demand immediate action by incorrectly interpreting warnings as forecasts and vice versa, which can lead to avoidable damages and even fatalities. We thus designed different action- and time-related icons (see ST5) that can be integrated into hazard messages and can quickly show people whether the information pertains to a past, present, or future event and whether they should take (immediate) action. In

addition, internal as well as external message consistency has to be ensured – the same action indication on the hazard message as on the overview – [60], avoiding any confusion [61].

2.3. Personal factors

The aim of event-related communication on multi-hazard platforms is to inform the public about current hazards and to provide them with the information needed to take action. Bean et al. [40] showed that people tend to first access further information to verify the content of the message. Further studies, in the context of earthquake early warning messages, have shown that people tend to not take any physical actions but rather to mentally prepare themselves [54,62,63]. In the context of weather forecasts, people who have not responded to prior warnings with a high chance will not respond to future warnings neither [43].

Though it is known that various personal factors influence these decision-making processes [9,18], the behavioral theories that are best suited to explain action-taking in a multi-hazard context remain to be explored [9].

This study examined the theory of planned behavior, according to which people's attitudes, norms, and perceived behavioral control influence their intention to take action [64,65]. According to Vinnell et al. [66], these factors predict people's intention to prepare for natural hazards. Grothmann and Reusswig [67] also reported that perceived behavioral control, for example, is positively related to the adoption intention of flood measures, whereas the results of Maddux and Rogers [68] showed no significant effect. To the best of our knowledge, our study is the first to assess the effects of people's experiential and instrumental attitudes, their injunctive and descriptive norms, and their perceived behavioral control on their intention to take (immediate) action and on their ability to correctly interpret information on multi-hazard platforms.

Since several studies have already shown that direct or indirect hazard experiences, as well as general or negative experiences, influence people's intention to take action and their capacity to correctly interpret information [34,69,70], this study also assessed people's hazard experiences. Since Misra et al. [58] demonstrated that, presently, emergency managers perceive a digital-based information overload, which negatively influences their decision-making, this study assessed whether people also perceive an information overload since a lot of information is simultaneously communicated on multi-hazard platforms. We also assessed whether sociodemographic characteristics influence people's intention to take action. Gender for example has been shown to influence people's interpretation capabilities of spatial information, including maps, with higher skills shown by men [71]. We thus assessed the following personal factors: gender [39,72], age, work position, educational degree [73], and living place.

Thus, we introduced a third research question (RQ3): *Do personal factors influence people's intention to take action and their ability to correctly interpret the information presented in multi-hazard overviews and hazard messages?*

3. Methodology and design

We applied a transdisciplinary research approach by involving experts in the design process and by testing the designs with end-users (Fig. 1a and 1b). To this end, we first conducted virtual workshops with experts from different fields to co-produce knowledge on how to best design hazard overviews and messages and refine them accordingly [74]. The fields of expertise ranged from climate risk modeling (critical infrastructure failures, tropical cyclones), over psychology (consumer behavior, public, risk perception, warning effectiveness) and political sciences (sustainable transition policies), to social ecology (sustainable development goals, circular economy) and communication sciences. This broad range of expertise ensured an effective cross-disciplinary discussion on how to improve the designs and that the complexity of the problem was grasped and theoretical and practical knowledge were linked [75]. Second, we conducted an online public survey to test whether the refined designs met the public's needs and expectations. We tested it with the general public because they are the main target audience of multi-hazard platforms. However, one has to keep in mind that

Fig. 1. 1a: Procedure of virtual workshops with scientists and practitioners from different fields [79,80]. The corresponding data and insights are listed in ST1–ST3. The icons are from <https://www.flaticon.com/>. 1b: The structure of the online public survey, where QB1 and QB2 contained between-subject experiments. The entire survey is in ST6. The icons are from <https://www.flaticon.com/>.

marginalized societal groups are most affected by (natural) hazards [76,77], and investigations are also needed to involve these groups and, consequently, to ensure disaster justice [78].

3.1. Virtual workshops with experts from different fields

In total, we conducted five virtual workshops on Zoom with three participants from July 21 to 29, 2021. Four of the five workshops were conducted with doctoral and post-doctoral students from different scientific fields (climate risk modeling, psychology, political science, and social ecology), and one workshop was conducted with practitioners (communication experts). Out of the participants, eleven were female, three male, and one “other.” The mean age was 28.5 years, ranging from 23 to 37 years.

The procedure of the virtual workshops was based on the results of one test run that allowed us to identify the tools that best fit the purpose of our workshops and how we could facilitate interactions. The workshops lasted about 1 h and consisted of four phases (Fig. 1a). The evaluated designs, the synthesized suggestions, and the raw data are listed in tables ST1 to ST3.

Regarding the analysis, participants’ written comments on the Mural and the transcribed group discussions were anonymized and analyzed with QDA Miner, a free software for qualitative analyses, according to the grounded theory approach. Suggestions for improvement were deduced from the data [81,82].

3.2. Designs

We designed the hazard overviews and hazard messages according to the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) and followed the recommendations of Padilla et al. [83] (see all versions in ST4 and ST5).

Regarding the hazard overviews, all the versions showed the same, for Switzerland possible, scenario (ST4), where the textual information was tailored to users’ locations to ensure that they felt personally affected [19]. Regarding the technical implementation in real world, this is possible either through cell broadcasting, access to users’ GPS location or pre-selected warning areas. To produce hazard overviews with overlapping and diverse information, the scenario contained cantonal and national messages, natural and technical hazards, and multiple active hazards in one canton. We included two for the Swiss public familiar hazards (thunderstorm and COVID-19 pandemic) and two less familiar hazards that are occurring (earthquakes) and have occurred in the past and are still in the public memory (chemical accidents) [84,85]. We chose this combination because we wanted to test how people perceive information about unexpected hazards in the context of on-going, well-known hazards. In total, we had 12 versions, and we varied two elements. First, we defined two hazard categorizations: a three-level categorization with “information, warning, alert” and a five-level categorization with “no to little danger, moderate danger, significant danger, high danger, very high danger.” Second, we had six different designs: a baseline (map on top, and below it a list without any time or action indication), a list (no map but time indication and an action-icon on the right), a time slider (map on top, and below it a time slider with time indication and an action-keyword)

Fig. 2. 2a: One of the baseline versions with a map but no time or action indications. 2b: One of the list versions with the time indication and action-icon on the right. 2c: One of the map versions with the time indication on the left and the action-keyword on the right. Note: These overviews are based on the five-level hazard categorization. The 12 overview versions are listed in ST4.

textual information below (map on top, and time indication and action-icon on the right), a map with textual information below (map on top, time indication on the left, and action-icon on the right), a map with textual information below (map on top, time indication on the left, and action-keyword on the right). The exemplary versions are presented in Fig. 2a–c.

All the hazard messages contained the same general information that was identified by several studies as indispensable (section 2.2): hazard type, affected areas, brief description, possible impacts, link to access further information, source, publication date. In total, we had 12 messages where we varied the hazard type (chemical accident-alert, thunderstorm-warning, and earthquake-information) and the time- and action-related icon (no icon, three-quarter circle, half circle, and vertical boxes). The three icon types and one exemplary version are presented in Fig. 3a and 3b.

3.3. Public survey

We conducted an online survey with two between-subjects experiments in Switzerland's German-speaking part from September 2 to 10, 2021. The survey was programmed in Unipark and pre-tested to improve the clarity of the questions and the technical functionalities. We performed a statistical power analysis using G*Power to calculate the required number of participants, which resulted in 500–600 participants [86]. The participants were recruited through the ISO-accredited polling company Respondi. We used quota sampling with quotas based on age and gender, representing Switzerland's average population. In total, 1045 people were recruited, with a completion rate of 58.6%. Due to short answer times (<5min) and failed quality checks, we excluded 32 participants [87].

The final 601 participants ranged in age from 18 to 85 years ($M = 46.29$, $SD = 16.56$), with 50.2% of them being female and 49.8% male. Most of the participants worked full-time (43.9%) or part-time (19.1%) and had either an apprenticeship certificate (39.6%), a Matura (15.6%), a technical college diploma (15.3%), or a university degree (12.8%). Additionally, most of them lived in the canton of Zurich (21.6%), followed by Bern (16.6%), St. Gallen (10.5%) and Aargau (10.1%). The detailed characteristics of the participants are listed in Table ST7. The sample characteristics – age, gender, education, living place, and work position – did not differ significantly across the experimental groups (Tables ST8a–c).

The survey consisted of four question blocks (QB), see Fig. 1b. In Appendix B2, we provide an overview of the core variables and of the studies from which we adapted the scales. In QB1, before the participants were randomly assigned to one of the 12 hazard overviews, they were introduced to a scenario. Using three question sets, we assessed their intention to take action, whether they correctly interpreted the information, and their general design perceptions (see Appendix B2 and Table ST9). Afterwards, in QB2, they were randomly assigned to one of the 12 hazard messages, and we assessed their intention to take action, their correct interpretation of the information, their general design perceptions, and their icon perceptions (see Appendix B2 and Table ST10). We further asked them

Fig. 3. 3a: The three icon types we tested displaying an alert. 3b: The exemplary message with the integrated three-quarter circle icon (all the message versions can be found in ST5).

whether some relevant information was missing from the message and which elements were especially useful for them (two open-ended questions). In QB3, we assessed the participants' experimental and instrumental attitudes, their perceived behavioral control, their injunctive and descriptive norms, and their perceived digital-based information overload. For all these variables, we used a five-point Likert scale, and they all showed good to excellent internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha >0.8), except for the variable "experiential attitudes" ($\alpha = 0.68$, $N = 4$) (see [Appendix B2](#)). Further, we assessed the participants' general and negative hazard experiences for all hazards displayed in the hazard overview [51] (see [Table ST11](#)). In QB4, we assessed the sociodemographic characteristics, namely gender, age, work position, living place, and highest educational degree (see [Table ST6](#) for the entire survey).

For the quantitative statistical analysis, we used SPSS, and for the qualitative analyses, we used QDA Miner. To analyze how the designs, the participants' general and negative hazard experiences, and their sociodemographic characteristics influenced their intention to take action and their ability to correctly interpret the information presented, we used several one-way analyses of variances (ANOVAs). Further, to analyze the effects of participants' experimental and instrumental attitudes, their perceived behavioral control, their injunctive and descriptive norms, and their perceived digital-based information overload on their intention to take action and their ability to correctly interpret the information presented, we used linear multiple regressions. Finally, to compare pairwise whether these differences were significant, we used Bonferroni post-hoc tests.

4. Results

The results are divided into two sections: section 4.1 for the hazard overviews ([Table 1](#)), and section 4.2 for the hazard messages ([Table 2](#)). We first summarize how the designs and personal factors affected the participants' intention to take action and their ability to correctly interpret the information. Second, we report the designs that were best rated by the participants.

4.1. Hazard overviews

4.1.1. Effects of the design on participants' intention to take action and their ability to correctly interpret the information

Aggregated over the 12 overview versions ([Appendix B2](#)), the participants had overall high intentions to take action ($M = 4.00$, $SD = 0.70$) and were most motivated to access further information ($M = 4.11$, $SD = 0.83$). Neither the design nor the hazard categorization had a significant effect ([Table 1](#) and [Table ST12](#)).

On average, the participants correctly answered five out of nine questions ($M = 5.39$, $SD = 1.76$) (see [Appendix B2](#)). As [Table 1](#) shows, compared to other design versions, the participants who saw a list answered significantly more questions correctly. They correctly interpreted that there was a nationwide COVID-19 message, that four hazard messages were available in the canton of Zurich, and that there were also active COVID-19 messages in the northeastern part of Switzerland ([Table ST9](#)). Further, the two designs with a map on top and textual information below (the time indication on the left and the action indication either as an icon or as a keyword on the right) were better interpreted than the baseline version without any time- and action-indication below the map ([Table 1](#)). The participants who saw a baseline version in particular struggled to understand that they still had time to prepare for an upcoming thunderstorm and that they should take immediate action regarding the chemical accident ([Table ST9](#)). Further, the majority of the participants who saw a version with the action-icon thought that the message related to the chemical accident told them to "run away" and not that "actions are needed" ([Table ST9](#)). In comparison, the participants who saw the action-keyword "act" significantly answered this question better. Hazard categorization thus did not have any significant effects ([Table 1](#)).

4.1.2. Effect of personal factors on people's intention to take action and their ability to correctly interpret the information

Regarding participants' intention to take action, we found three significant effects ([Tables ST14a/b](#)). First, the higher the participants' instrumental attitudes ($\beta = 0.17$, $p < .001$), injunctive norms ($\beta = 0.15$, $p = .01$), and descriptive norms ($\beta = 0.12$, $p = .04$), the higher their intention to take action ($R^2 = 0.19$, $F(6,594) = 24.29$, $p < .001$). Second, the participants who had already experienced a chemical accident ($M = 4.21$, $SD = 0.60$) or a pandemic ($M = 4.04$, $SD = 0.66$) had a higher intention to take immediate action compared to those without any such experiences ($M = 3.98$, $SD = 0.70$ / $M = 3.84$, $SD = 0.97$). Third, the participants who had already been negatively affected by a thunderstorm ($M = 4.13$, $SD = 0.61$) were likelier to take action compared to those without such experiences ($M = 3.96$, $SD = 0.72$). The participants' sociodemographic characteristics showed no significant effects ([Table ST15](#)).

Regarding the ability to correctly interpret the information, we found four significant effects ([Tables ST14a/b](#)). First, the higher the participants' perceived behavioral control, the higher their number of correctly answered questions ($\beta = 0.36$, $p = .02$). Second, the participants who had already experienced a pandemic answered more questions correctly ($M = 5.54$, $SD = 1.70$) than those without such experiences ($M = 4.61$, $SD = 1.83$). In particular, they answered correctly that there was an active nationwide COVID-19 message. Third, the participants between 18 and 30 years ($M = 5.81$, $SD = 1.71$) answered more questions correctly than the participants between 50 and 60 years ($M = 5.17$, $SD = 1.83$). Fourth, men ($M = 5.61$, $SD = 1.71$) answered more questions correctly than women ($M = 5.18$, $SD = 1.78$) ([Table ST15](#)).

4.1.3. General design perception

Aggregated over all 12 versions ([Appendix B2](#)), the hazard overviews were rated as useful ($M = 4.08$, $SD = 0.78$) and trustworthy ($M = 3.92$, $SD = 0.80$). In contrast, the content could have been more clearly arranged ($M = 3.45$, $SD = 1.09$) and was not always perceived as completely understandable ($M = 3.59$, $SD = 1.00$).

There were no significant effects with respect to the two hazard categorizations but with respect to the designs ([Table 1](#)). The list version received a significantly better rating than the baseline, the map with the time slider below, and the map with textual information below (time indication on the left and action-keyword on the right). Further, the version with the map and textual information below (time indication on the left and action-icon on the right) was significantly better rated than the map with the time slider.

Table 1

The effects of the design versions and the hazard categorization on participants' intention to take action, ability to correctly interpret the information, and general design perceptions [N = 601]. The further corresponding tables are listed in the supplements ST9, ST12, and ST13a/b.

		n	Intention to take action		Correct interpretation		Design perception	
			Mean (SD)	One-Way ANOVA	Mean (SD)	One-Way ANOVA	Mean (SD)	One-Way ANOVA
Hazard categorization	3-level categorization [information, warning, alert]	309	3.96 (0.72)	F(1,599) = 2.381, p = .123, $\eta^2 = 0.004$	5.44 (1.79)	F(1,599) = 0.465, p = .496, $\eta^2 < 0.001$	3.70 (0.82)	F(1,599) = 0.440, p = .507, $\eta^2 < 0.001$
	5-level categorization [no to little danger, moderate danger, significant danger, high danger, very high danger]	292	4.05 (0.67)		5.34 (1.72)		3.74 (0.69)	
Design version	Baseline [map on top, below a list without any time and action indication]	90	3.99 (0.74)	F(5, 595) = 0.599, p = .701, $\eta^2 = 0.005$	4.69 (1.53)^{b,e,f}	F(5, 595) = 10.773, p < .001, $\eta^2 = 0.09$	3.56 (0.75)^b	F(5, 595) = 6.619, p < .001, $\eta^2 = 0.06$
	List [no map, time indication and an action-icon on the right]	105	3.93 (0.79)		6.30 (1.62)^{a,c,d,e,f}		3.97 (0.67)^{a,c,f}	
	Timeslider [map on top, below timelider with time indication and action-keyword]	95	3.96 (0.73)		5.01 (1.81)^b		3.46 (0.81)^{b,e}	
	Map + Text 1 [map on top, time indication and action-icon on the right]	110	4.03 (0.64)		5.18 (1.73)^b		3.77 (0.76)	
	Map + Text 2 [map on top, time indication on the left and action-icon on the right]	102	4.05 (0.58)		5.52 (1.70)^{a,b}		3.87 (0.72)^c	
	Map + Text 3 [map on top, time indication on the left and action-keyword on the right]	99	4.07 (0.69)		5.52 (1.73)^{a,b}		3.64 (0.77)^b	
	The twelve overviews	O1a [3-level cat. – baseline]	43	3.98 (0.79)	F(11,589) = 0.701, p = .738, $\eta^2 = 0.01$	4.72 (1.55)^{b,h}	F(11,589) = 6.180, p < .001, $\eta^2 = 0.12$	3.54 (0.90)^b
	O2a [3-level cat. – list]	51	3.83 (0.90)		6.35 (1.75)^{a,d,f,g,i}		3.83 (0.74)	
	O3a [3-level cat. – timeslider]	48	3.95 (0.77)		5.54 (1.77)		3.34 (0.89)^{e,h}	
	O4a [3-level cat. – map + text 1]	57	3.93 (0.70)		5.12 (1.82)^{b,h}		3.80 (0.80)	
	O5a [3-level cat. – map + text 2]	63	4.05 (0.56)		5.57 (1.65)ⁱ		3.94 (0.73)^c	
	O6a [3-level cat. – map + text 3]	47	4.02 (0.64)		5.19 (1.84)^b		3.63 (0.79)	
	O1b [5-level cat. – baseline]	47	3.99 (0.70)		4.66 (1.54)^{b,h,l}		3.58 (0.59)^b	
	O2b [5-level cat. – list]	54	4.03 (0.67)		6.26 (1.49)^{a,d,g,i}		4.10 (0.56)^{a,c,g,i}	
	O3b [5-level cat. – timeslider]	47	3.96 (0.68)		4.47 (1.70)^{b,e,h,l}		3.58 (0.70)^b	
	O4b [5-level cat. – map + text 1]	53	4.13 (0.56)		5.25 (1.63)		3.74 (0.71)	
	O5b [5-level cat. – map + text 2]	39	4.06 (0.63)		5.44 (1.79)		3.77 (0.69)	
	O6b [5-level cat. – map + text 3]	52	4.11 (0.74)		5.81 (1.58)^{g,i}		3.65 (0.76)	

Note: The significant values are highlighted in bold. The scales for the variables “intention to take action” and “design perception” range from 1 to 5. The range for the variable “correct interpretation” is 0–9.

Table 2

The effects of hazard type and icon type on participants' intention to take action, ability to correctly interpret the information, and design perceptions [N = 601]. The further corresponding tables are listed in the supplements ST10, ST16, and ST17a/b.

		n	Intention to take action		Correct interpretation		Design perception	
			Mean (SD)	One-Way ANOVA	Mean (SD)	One-Way ANOVA	Mean (SD)	One-Way ANOVA
Hazard type	Earthquake	195	3.52 (0.86) ^{b,c}	F(2,598) = 39.750, p < .001, $\eta^2 = 0.13$	2.44 (1.02) ^c	F(2,598) = 12.560, p < .001, $\eta^2 = 0.04$	4.13 (0.56) ^b	F(2,598) = 7.729, p < .001, $\eta^2 = 0.03$
	Chemical accident	198	4.22 (0.70) ^{a,c}		2.41 (0.78) ^c		4.28 (0.59) ^{a,c}	
	Thunderstorm	208	3.82 (0.79) ^{a,b}		2.05 (0.81) ^{a,b}		4.05 (0.64) ^b	
Icon type	No icon [Baseline]	150	3.71 (0.86) ^c	F(3,597) = 3.460, p = .016, $\eta^2 = 0.02$	2.29 (0.98)	F(5, 595) = 10.773, p < .001, $\eta^2 = 0.09$	4.15 (0.64)	F(3,597) = 0.662, p = .576, $\eta^2 = 0.003$
	Three-quarter circle	144	3.93 (0.76)		2.24 (0.90)		4.09 (0.65)	
	Half circle	159	3.98 (0.79) ^a		2.31 (0.74)		4.18 (0.56)	
	Vertical boxes	148	3.79 (0.90)		2.32 (0.93)		4.18 (0.57)	
The twelve message versions	Earthquake message with three-quarter circle	49	3.76 (0.75) ^{e,g}	F(11,589) = 8.915, p < .001, $\eta^2 = 0.17$	2.29 (1.04)	F(11,589) = 6.180, p < .001, $\eta^2 = 0.12$	4.16 (0.53)	F(11,589) = 2.196, p = .013, $\eta^2 = 0.04$
	Earthquake message with half circle	42	3.65 (0.78) ^{e,f,h}		2.55 (0.80)		4.20 (0.48)	
	Earthquake message baseline	54	3.40 (0.90) ^{e,f,g,h,j}		2.48 (1.06)		4.13 (0.64)	
	Earthquake message with vertical boxes	50	3.30 (0.93) ^{e,f,g,h,j}		2.44 (1.11)		4.04 (0.56)	
	Chemical accident message with three-quarter circle	51	4.24 (0.74) ^{b,c,d}		2.33 (0.91)		4.17 (0.71)	
	Chemical accident message with half circle	54	4.31 (0.71) ^{a,b,c,d,k,l}		2.33 (0.67)		4.34 (0.49)	
	Chemical accident message baseline	45	3.99 (0.69) ^{e,d}		2.47 (0.87)		4.25 (0.64)	
	Chemical accident message with vertical boxes	48	4.31 (0.60) ^{a,b,c,d}		2.52 (0.65)		4.36 (0.50) ⁱ	
	Thunderstorm message with three-quarter circle	44	3.78 (0.69)		2.09 (0.71)		3.93 (0.67) ^h	
	Thunderstorm message with half circle	63	3.91 (0.76) ^{e,d}		2.14 (0.72)		4.02 (0.64)	
	Thunderstorm message baseline	51	3.79 (0.83) ^f		1.94 (0.90)		4.09 (0.64)	
	Thunderstorm message with vertical boxes	50	3.85 (0.83) ^f		2.00 (0.90)		4.15 (0.60)	

Note: The significant values are highlighted in bold. The scales for the variables "intention to take action" and "design perception" range from 1 to 5. The range for the variable "correct interpretation" is 0–4.

4.2. Hazard messages

4.2.1. Effect of the design on people's intention to take action and their ability to correctly interpret the information

Aggregated over the 12 hazard messages (Appendix B1), the participants had the highest motivation to take the recommended actions listed on the message (M = 4.06, SD = 0.88). Further, we have several significant effects regarding the hazard type and the icon type (Table 2 and Table ST16). Regarding the hazard type, the participants who saw a chemical accident message had a significantly higher intention to take action than those who saw an earthquake or a thunderstorm message. Further, the participants who saw a thunderstorm message had a significantly higher intention to take action than those who saw an earthquake message (Table 2). Regarding icon type, the participants who saw one of the messages with the half circle had a significantly higher intention to take action than those who saw a baseline message without an icon (Table 2).

With an open-answer question, the participants were able to specify the elements that were most useful to them. We identified that, for all three hazard types, the information about possible impacts, the behavioral recommendations, and the indication of the hazard type/severity motivated the participants the most to take action or at least to access further information. For the chemical accident messages in particular, the icon on the top-right ("Act now") motivated them to take action. Additionally, it also mattered whether people felt personally affected; women especially stated that they felt personally affected and, in turn, showed a higher intention to take the recommended actions. In comparison, for men, it was most important to access further information on, for example, news

portals (Table ST21).

Regarding participants' ability to correctly interpret the information, it shows that the participants, on average, correctly answered two out of four questions ($M = 2.29$, $SD = 0.89$) (see Appendix B2). They especially were not sure whether the possible impact mentioned in the message would occur. Additionally, the majority thought that the most important recommended action was the one at the top of the list (Table ST10). The icon type showed no significant effect, whereas the hazard type did (Table 2). The participants who saw a thunderstorm message answered significantly fewer questions correctly than those who saw an earthquake or chemical accident message (Table 2). They especially struggled to understand that they still had time to prepare (Table ST10).

4.2.2. Effect of personal factors on participants' intention to take action and their ability to correctly interpret the information

Regarding the intention to take action, the higher the participants' instrumental attitudes ($\beta = -0.24$, $p < .001$) and the higher their injunctive norms ($\beta = -0.34$, $p < .001$), the higher their intention to take action (Tables ST19a/b). Further, the hazard messages made women ($M = 3.94$, $SD = 0.79$) more significantly triggered to take action than men ($M = 3.76$, $SD = 0.87$). Moreover, the full-time employed participants ($M = 3.72$, $SD = 0.91$) were significantly less triggered by the hazard messages to take action than full-time housewives/househusbands ($M = 4.13$, $SD = 0.67$) and those who retired ($M = 3.98$, $SD = 0.74$) (see Table ST20).

Regarding the participant's ability to correctly interpret the information, the lower the participants' experiential attitudes ($\beta = -0.15$, $p = .03$) or the higher the participants' perceived behavioral control ($\beta = 0.25$, $p = .001$), the higher their number of correctly answered questions (Tables ST19a/b). The participants' sociodemographic characteristics showed no significant effects on their ability to correctly interpret the information (Table ST20).

4.2.3. General design and icon perception

Aggregated over all the message versions, the designs were rated very good (all means > 4.05 ; see Table 2 and Tables ST17a/b). The icon type exerted no significant effect on the participants' general perceptions of the hazard messages. In comparison, the hazard type exerted a significant effect (Table 2). The chemical accident messages were significantly better rated than the earthquake or thunderstorm messages.

Regarding the perception of the time- and action-related icon, the majority of the participants stated (Table ST8d) that the icon made it easier for them to understand whether the message was about an event that already happened, is ongoing, or will soon occur ($M = 4.07$, $SD = 0.92$). Further, they thought that the icon was overall useful ($M = 4.00$, $SD = 0.90$). In comparison, the icon did not really motivate them to read the message ($M = 2.27$, $SD = 1.19$).

4.2.4. Missing information

Overall, for 389 participants, the messages contained all the information they needed, and for 64, some information was missing (Table ST22). The chemical accident message had no link to an external website, which some of the participants criticized. In addition, some of them wanted a more precise description of what happened and to know how long the event would last – i.e., for how long they had to follow the recommended action. For the earthquake and thunderstorm messages, the participants wished for more detailed information about them, such as the evolution of the thunderstorm.

5. Discussion

In this chapter, we answer the three RQs: whether the design of the hazard overviews/messages (RQ1) or the personal factors (RQ3) influence people's intention to take action and their ability to correctly interpret the information. Further, we discuss whether the best-rated designs are also the ones that increase people's intention to take action and help them correctly interpret the information (RQ2). The chapter ends by discussing the limitations of this study and future research needs (section 5.4).

5.1. The influence of the design (RQ1)

That the hazard information disseminated to the public prompts people to take action and is correctly interpreted is paramount. Misunderstanding relevant information can trigger inappropriate behaviors and, in turn, worsen emergency situations. In sections 5.1.1 and 5.1.2, we offer design recommendations for hazard overviews and messages that are actionable but can also be correctly understood. Thereby, it is crucial that especially people affected by a hazard or those interested in the affected regions (e.g., family's living place) receive the messages [55]. Since cell broadcasting is legally not allowed in Switzerland, we recommend that people can pre-select warning areas they are interested in or to ask them to allow access to their GPS location.

5.1.1. On people's intention to take action

We found that people have a high intention to look for further information if they see a hazard overview (Fig. 4). In comparison, adding a time- and action-related icon – especially our half-circle icon – to a hazard message significantly increased people's intention to take the recommended actions (Fig. 5). As these insights emphasize, people initially tend to seek further information since what is displayed on an overview is not sufficient to decide their next step. Thoughtfully designed hazard messages linked to the overview can help people take action without having to leave the platform, thus reducing milling [40]. Additionally, instead of fancy and complex designs, clear and simple words that address the actionability of the information are needed.

Regarding the hazard overviews, our two hazard categorizations – the three-level categorization with “information, warning, alert” and the five-level categorization with “no to little danger, moderate danger, significant danger, high danger, very high danger” – showed no significant differences, supporting the results of our prior study [17]. This may imply that it does not matter which hazard categorization one uses as far as the levels are clearly defined and related to the urgency to take action and the severity of a hazard.

However, the possibility of people misunderstanding hazard levels has to always be considered [40], as it can lead to inaction or unintended panic. Further, the participants who were randomly assigned to an earthquake or a thunderstorm message stated in the comment field that they would have liked to see more information about the chemical accident, as it seemed to be the most urgent hazard. This implies that our chosen hazard categorizations showed them which hazards demanded immediate action.

Regarding the actionability of the hazard messages, we confirmed the findings of prior studies: information about possible impacts, behavioral recommendations, and the hazard level increase people's intention to take action [43,52,53]. We also demonstrated that people tend to react proportionally to the severity and urgency of the hazard [39,52], i.e., chemical accident messages (high urgency) increased their intention to take action. We additionally showed that a time- and action-related icon, especially the half circle, significantly increased people's intention to take action, which is in line with the findings of Kreuzmair et al. [47] that visual elements such as pictograms increase the public's comprehension and compliance with warning information. The positive effect of the icon is especially high when the hazard is more urgent. Thus, including a time- and action-related icon on hazard messages not only helps people understand the timing of an event but also increases their intention to take action [41]. Moreover, as all the designs were perceived well, integrating such an icon ensures messages' clarity and clear structure.

5.1.2. On people's ability to correctly interpret the information

The most common misinterpretation related to hazard overviews was that the action-icon made people think of running away and not taking immediate action. Thus, we recommend using keywords such as "prepare, inform, and act," since they can be correctly understood and trigger people to the same extent as the action-icons to take action. This is in line with the recommendations of Estuar et al. [41] to work with relevant keywords. Alternatively, one could test other icons to ensure their unambiguity. Additionally, we showed that hazard overviews without any time and action indication leave people struggling to understand what they should/have to

Fig. 4. The two hazard overviews that were correctly interpreted and triggered people the most to take action. We recommend that the list below the map be tailored to the users' locations or to pre-selected regions. Further, users should be able to switch between the two formats, as they each have their own advantages and, in combination, best meet people's needs and expectations. The hazard categorization can also be replaced by "no to little danger, moderate danger, significant danger, high danger, very high danger," since the two hazard categorizations have the same effects.

do.

Regarding the hazard messages, our designed icons ensured that people understood whether the messages were related to an event that was approaching, happening, or ending. The icons thus help avoid misconceptions about whether a message is a forecast or a post-event message, as identified by Valenzuela Rodriguez [10]. Consequently, icons ensure that people take the right actions at the right time. For example, for the thunderstorm message, the icon made it clear that there was still time to prepare. However, we identified two further misconceptions caused by certain design elements. First, people thought that the most important recommended action was the one at the top. However, it is often not possible to rank the recommendations since they are tailored to different locations; for instance, when they feel the ground shake, people driving a car should take different actions than the people sitting at a table inside a building. Thus, the recommended actions are often equally important. In light of this misconception, in situations where one specific action is extremely important, this action can be placed at the top to better capture people’s attention. Further, if technology allows, the order of the recommended actions could be tailored to the users’ current location (outside vs. inside a building) so that the action relevant to them is at the top. Second, compared with post-event messages, people struggled to understand whether the expected impacts conveyed by forecasts – a thunderstorm forecast, in our case – would actually occur. One option may be to communicate the probabilities and uncertainties of the expected impacts [88,89]. However, further research is needed to explore how to best communicate such uncertainties and probabilities [90].

Fig. 5. The hazard messages with the most effective time- and action-related icon (the half-circle icon) for three different hazards. Including an icon is thus important not only for forecasts but also for ongoing hazards or post-event information.

5.2. General perception vs. triggers of actions (RQ2)

The experts who participated in our virtual workshops and our finding that hazard overviews with maps are considered the most useful and trustworthy confirmed the findings of past studies that people prefer maps (e.g., Ref. [17]). However, we showed that the information presented in a list is better understood and perceived as better structured compared to designs that include a map. This is in line with Marti's et al. [27] and Meyer's et al. [35], who analyzed earthquake and flood maps, respectively. Despite this, the experts from our workshops stressed that maps help people quickly see hazard hotspots [24], allowing them to check whether they are personally affected [19].

Regarding the hazard overviews in particular, the well-perceived designs were mainly those that were correctly interpreted. There was only one difference: the hazard overviews with the action-icon were better perceived than those with the action-keyword. However, the action-icon was ambiguous and misinterpreted by the majority: they thought they should run away, which is actually the opposite of what they should do (stay inside and close the windows). We thus recommend replacing action-icons with action-keywords. Further, since the design had no effect on people's intention to take action, the general perception can help choose the appropriate design – in our case, this was the list and the map with the time- and action-oriented textual information below it. It is also important for the user location to be marked on the map and the information to be tailored to this location so that users can check whether they are affected.

Regarding the hazard messages, the three time- and action-related icons were similarly perceived and had no effect on people's ability to interpret information correctly. In comparison, icon type influenced people's intention to take action. In light of this, we recommend that the half-circle icon, including a reference to the event timing and the recommended action, should be integrated into hazard messages to increase their actionability.

To conclude, since all our designs were well perceived, they offer excellent guidance in the development of (multi-)hazard overviews and specific hazard messages. In addition, our assessment of people's capability to correctly interpret the information and their intention to take action allowed us to identify the most actionable and understandable information elements. We thus recommend not only assessing people's preferences for and general perceptions of certain designs but also conducting experimental studies to test the designs that prompt people to take action and can be clearly understood.

5.3. The influence of personal factors (RQ3)

We found that not only the design of the overview/messages but also people's personal factors influenced their intention to take action as well as their ability to correctly interpret the information.

Our results confirmed that people's *past hazard experiences* influence their intention to take action [69]. In particular, their general experience with pandemics increases their ability to correctly interpret hazard overviews and their positive perceptions of hazard messages. This is in line with Becker et al. [34], who showed that during an ongoing hazard (sequence), people become familiar with the information and better understand it. Thus, we conclude that people who receive warning messages for hazards and regions they are familiar with know what they can and should do and better understand the behavioral recommendations provided by the authorities in charge. Locally relevant information in addition increases people's personal risk perception and, in turn, intention to take action [42]. Further, although everyone should have ticked in the questionnaire that they have experienced a pandemic, some participants indicated otherwise. They might think they are unaffected by the current COVID-19 pandemic or think that it is not real and invented by the government. Such people are often against authoritative information, which is in line with our study results since these participants were less triggered by the hazard messages to take action.

Regarding perceived behavioral control, our findings are in line with the results of prior studies that high perceived behavioral control positively affects people's intention to take action [66,67], and thus stands in contrast with the results of the studies that showed no effect [68]. Further, we showed that people with high levels of perceived behavioral control can better understand and perceive the information on hazard overviews and hazard messages.

Regarding people's attitudes and norms, we showed that high levels of instrumental attitudes and injunctive norms lead to a higher intention to take action, thus confirming the results of Vinnell et al. [66]. Further, high levels of experiential attitudes lead to a better perception of hazard overviews but decrease the ability to correctly interpret hazard messages. Additionally, the higher the descriptive norms, the higher the people's intention to take action due to hazard overviews.

Our findings concerning the effects of socio-demographic characteristics are in line with the results of other studies. We also showed that men [71] – who especially appreciate a link to access more information [55] – and younger people are better at interpreting maps. The latter effect may be explained by the fact that younger people are more familiar with apps with similar content and formats. Moreover, women, housewives/househusbands, and retired people have a higher intention to take action [39,72], which could be because women and retired people have higher levels of risk perception [91] and housewives/househusbands feel responsible for protecting their children at home. Unlike the results of Balluz et al. [73], the educational degree showed no significant effect on people's intention to take action in our study.

5.4. Limitations and future research

Our findings concerning the designs are restricted to the attributes we varied for the different multi-hazard overviews and specific hazard messages. Concerning the overviews, we tested quite complex designs with various overlapping information elements; however, the participants did not seem to be (cognitively) overwhelmed. Further, since we did not specifically assess information complexity, future research should explore questions such as the following: What is the upper threshold of the information that can be presented on a single map that will facilitate its correct interpretation? How many different hazards can be simultaneously displayed

on a single map without negatively affecting people's compliance with taking action?

Regarding personal factors, we offer insights into how people's intention to take action when confronted with multi-hazard information is influenced by the factors of the theory of planned behavior. These insights can serve as a basis for further studies following, for example, the approach of Vinnell et al. [66], who applied a structural equation model. Further research is also needed to determine the proportions of the population that have specific beliefs, global beliefs, and no beliefs at all about the potential hazards to which they are exposed and the actions they can take to protect themselves [18]. Moreover, we only assessed people's personal experiences with the hazards and their effects on their intention to take action. However, Miranda et al. [70], who researched the adoption of structural strengthening as an earthquake preparedness action, showed that indirect experiences – family or friends having experienced losses – can also trigger action and influence people's preparedness decisions.

Regarding the sample of our study, the participants represented the general public in the German speaking part of Switzerland regarding age, gender and highest educational degree. As a matter of resources, we did not specifically consider marginalized societal groups. However, especially those are the groups the most affected by (natural) hazards [76,77]. We thus want to test in a next step whether our developed designs are also suitable for these groups or how the designs must be adjusted to fulfill their specific needs. Overall, more efforts are needed to consider disaster justice and to involve especially marginalized societal groups in disaster management planning [78].

Our experiments were hypothetical and did not reflect decision-making under real circumstances. However, we used a between-subjects experiment that, as Weyrich et al. [92] discussed, represented people's real-world behavior. Further, we used a realistic scenario with two for the public familiar hazards (thunderstorm and COVID-19 pandemic) and two hazards that do not occur that frequently but can cause significant damages (earthquake and chemical accident). Thus, people must be able to handle information about these hazards in their daily lives. Still, future studies should test the developed hazard overviews and hazard messages in real-world situations. In Switzerland, for example, the new information elements – action- and time- related icons – could be added to the messages disseminated via the two existing multi-hazard apps. Using short questionnaires after different events, information can be gained regarding the actions the users took and whether the information was useful. To directly measure this, these questionnaires should be ready before new information products are released.

6. Conclusion

The hazard overviews and messages we designed (Figs. 4 and 5) are actionable, correctly understood, and well perceived. Regarding the hazard overviews, time indication and action-keywords should be integrated. We recommend a map above a list with information about the affected areas, the time of dissemination (before, during, or after the event), and the recommended actions (prepare, inform, act). This enhances people's comprehension of the information and their intention to access further information. Regarding the hazard messages, we confirmed the importance of the following information elements: hazard type and level, affected areas, time, behavioral recommendations, possible impacts, and source. Additionally, we recommend the addition of a time- and action-related icon since we found that such an icon motivates people to take action and ensures that they understand whether they should take immediate action or still have time to prepare for the event. Moreover, a better understanding of the personal factors influencing people's intention to take action and their ability to correctly interpret the information presented allows communication platforms to be tailored to specific skills and address the various groups' needs, such as providing maps for men and written explanations for women.

Finally, we were only able to gain these insights by applying a transdisciplinary research approach and an experimental study design. We thus encourage researchers to test the designs experimentally and include end-users in the development processes to increase the platforms' effectiveness and usefulness.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2022.102917>.

Appendix B. Study design and the most relevant variables of the survey

Appendix B1. Overview of the study design and the research questions

Appendix B2. The most relevant survey variables

	Items	Mean ^a	SD	α [# items]	Reference [adapted from]
Dependent variables	Hazard overview: Intention to take action				[64]
	Average sum variable	4.00	0.70	.83 [N = 4]	
	<i>I intend to access more information.</i>	4.11	0.83		
	<i>I intend to forward the information to friends and relatives.</i>	4.00	0.91		
	<i>I intend to take immediate action.</i>	3.94	0.88		
	<i>I intend to prepare for events that will occur soon.</i>	3.98	0.80		
	Hazard overview: Correct interpretation				
	Sum variable	5.39	1.76		
	Hazard message: Intention to take actions				[64]
	Average sum variable	3.85	0.83	.81 [N = 3]	
	<i>I intend to look for more information.</i>	3.74	1.00		
	<i>I intend to forward the information to friends and relatives.</i>	3.77	1.06		
	<i>I intend to take the recommended actions.</i>	4.06	0.88		
	Hazard message: Correct interpretation				
	Sum variable	2.29	0.89		
	Hazard overview: Design perception				[27]
	Average sum variable	3.72	0.76	.89 [N = 6]	
	<i>Useful</i>	4.08	0.78		
	<i>Trustworthy</i>	3.92	0.80		
	<i>Understandable</i>	3.59	1.00		
<i>Well structured</i>	3.61	0.97			
<i>Appealingly designed</i>	3.66	0.98			
<i>Clearly arranged</i>	3.45	1.09			
Hazard message: Design perception				[27]	
Average sum variables	4.15	0.60	.93 [N = 6]		
<i>Useful</i>	4.25	0.69			
<i>Understandable</i>	4.17	0.67			
<i>Appealingly designed</i>	4.07	0.74			
<i>Clearly arranged</i>	4.14	0.71			
<i>Trustworthy</i>	4.17	0.68			
<i>Well structured</i>	4.11	0.69			

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Items	Mean ^a	SD	α [# items]	Reference [adapted from]
Hazard message: Icon perception				
Average sum variable	3.61	0.62	.66 [N = 6]	
<i>Is useful</i>	4.00	0.90		
<i>Is appealingly designed</i>	3.75	1.03		
<i>Is needed</i>	3.73	1.04		
<i>Motivates me to read the message</i>	2.27	1.19		
<i>Makes it easier for me to understand what I need to do</i>	3.81	1.00		
<i>Makes it easier for me to understand whether the message is about an event that has already happened, is ongoing, or will occur soon.</i>	4.07	0.92		
Institutional attitudes				[64,66,93]
Average sum variable	4.20	0.88	.89 [N = 4]	
<i>Useless → useful</i>	4.24	0.99		
<i>Unimportant → important</i>	4.24	0.96		
<i>Unnecessary → necessary</i>	4.14	1.03		
<i>Pointless → valuable</i>	4.19	1.10		
Experiential attitudes				[64,66,93]
Average sum variable	3.55	0.71	.68 [N = 4]	
<i>Complicated → simple</i>	3.91	1.00		
<i>Boring → enjoyable</i>	3.10	0.88		
<i>Unpleasant → pleasant</i>	3.14	1.05		
<i>Unrewarding → rewarding</i>	4.03	1.05		
Perceived behavioral control				[64,66,93]
Average sum variable	4.18	0.58	.85 [N = 5]	
<i>I would be able to take the recommended actions (e.g., have the necessary resources).</i>	4.10	0.74		
<i>If I want to, I could take the recommended actions.</i>	4.18	0.75		
<i>It is easy for me to take the recommended actions.</i>	4.04	0.74		
<i>The decision to take the recommended actions is within my control.</i>	4.20	0.75		
<i>It is up to me to take the recommended actions.</i>	4.36	0.68		
Injunctive norms				[64,66,93]
Average sum variable	4.05	0.69	.92 [N = 3]	
<i>Most people who are important to me approve of my decision to take the recommended actions.</i>	4.09	0.73		
<i>Most people like me approve my decision to take the recommended actions.</i>	4.02	0.75		
<i>The people in my life whose opinion I value approve of my decision to take the recommended actions.</i>	4.05	0.75		
Descriptive norms				[64,66,93]
Average sum variable	3.96	0.66	.92 [N = 3]	
<i>Most people who are important to me usually take the recommended actions.</i>	3.99	0.70		
<i>Most people like me usually take the recommended actions.</i>	3.93	0.72		
<i>The people in my life whose opinion I value usually take the recommended actions.</i>	3.95	0.70		
Perceived digital-based information overload				[58]
Average sum variable	2.83	0.90	.86 [N = 4]	
<i>You have too much information and communication channels to manage on your mobile devices (e.g., emails, text messages, Twitter feeds, push messages).</i>	2.87	1.10		
<i>You need too much time to manage the different digital information.</i>	2.85	1.02		
<i>You are being pushed to use multiple electronic information and communication means at the same time (by your personal or work environment).</i>	2.75	1.11		
<i>You are under pressure to react as quickly as possible to digital news or messages.</i>	2.85	1.06		

^a The scale for all the variables ranged from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree, except for the variable "correct interpretation." For the hazard overviews, 0–9 correct answers were possible, and for the hazard messages, 0–4 correct answers were possible [N = 601].

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